

Paper 12

**THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN MAKING THE
YOUTH AS THE FUTURE LEADERS OF THE
LARGEST DEMOCRACY OF THE WORLD-A STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

'Indian Youth are not useless but they are used less'. Swami Vivekananda. When we speak about the Indian youth and their induction into politics certainly the words of Swami Vivekananda implies. Youth can be the leaders of tomorrow if we procrastinate. Indian youth who has good leadership, skill and technically advanced are able to view the situation with clear educative perspective and more humane outlook. In this paper an attempt is made to analyze, why the Indian youth is disinterested in entering into politics. What is their vision about themselves with regard to their future, politics and nation? The societal, economic and parenthesis factors influence the youth in taking a decision about their future perspective. An attempt is made to trace the role of education in bringing up the future leaders who would lead the largest democracy of the world. The need of research in this regard as present scenario of Indian politics has a social stigma. It is believed that education, training and inspiration can bring forth great leaders in various fields; likewise it could be made possible in politics. But it is a long way for the youth to go. An attempt made in this paper whether the educated youth will be able to write one's own success story withstanding all the odds like the absence of role models, divided interest, power hunger, criminalization of the politics, use of money, muscle, and mafia, interference of religious bodies, caste politics along with other social aspects and many more. Education is the only channel that can bring in change but the current pattern and system is not been able to bring out the politicians who have not compromised with principles and ethics. In this paper an attempt is made to bring around the youth and politics through education.

Keywords: Youth, education, politics, society, leader.

1. INTRODUCTION

The youth in politics is the subject of debate and lauded that they are the future of the country and only they can bring in change. The youth who are also called as techno-youth form the largest number and able to sustain any type of change and challenge that comes forth. Youth who are in between the age of 18 and 35 are enthusiastic energetic and full of innovative

ideas and spirit. There are divided opinions about the youth entering into politics. Government of India has given the right to vote who have completed 18 years which was formerly 21 years. This is a clear indication that the Government of India understands that the youth have the responsibility and wisdom to elect the representatives who would rule the country. Thereby the induction of the youth in politics and their participation is valid. Election and the franchise is a part of democracy and exercising the right to vote is a bonded duty of every citizen but participating actively in the politics begins the formation of a future leader. Education should help the youth to apply their own rationality. India is the biggest democracy of the world. It is people who use their power through election but electing the righteous one makes the difference. To make this difference one has to be the keen observer and constant follower of the day today happening. He need to acquire information of all the sectors of the society may it be agriculture, industry, education, health, foreign affairs, environment so on and so forth. This will make the youth to understand his responsibility in casting vote. The educational institutions should take up the idea to promote the interest of the students in political science. The institutions could initiate programs at various levels of education right from the secondary level. The need of the hour is to change the superficial perception that politics is not suitable for the educated and decent people.

2.REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sanjay Kumar in his book Indian Youth and Electoral Politics-An Emerging Engagement is of the opinion that over the decades the youth are participating more actively in politics and at certain level they are targeted the 'vote banks'. He says that 'The level of political awareness of Indian youth is much higher than among the adults and in the coming years they will be the biggest contributing factor to the political change in the country'. He is also of the opinion that in the upcoming elections the youth will be 'catalyst behind the change in the country. The book also throws light on why the youth of the country are more likely to vote for a young candidate than an older candidate during the next elections.

3.OBJECTIVES

- To highlight the need of youth in politics.
- Vision of the youth with regard to their future perspective and politics.
- To throw light on the present situation in Indian politics.
- To analyze the role of education and the development in Indian Universities.
- To find a via media that can attract the youth towards politics through education.

4.METHODOLOGY: This is an evaluative review of the youth in politics and the role of education. The role of education along with other factors is analyzed in bringing up the next generation leaders and the challenges and the solutions for better prospects. This is a conceptual study based on the primary and secondary sources. The study is descriptive in nature.

HYPOTHESIS: Youth make a success story in politics through education.

5. ANALYSIS:

Mahatma Gandhi had given a call to the young to take part in the national movement. Taking his call many youngsters entered into the national movement and some of them led the movement and later they became the torch bearers of the country. Democracy needs the young enthusiastic, energetic, dynamic, foresighted leaders to lead the country. In India the ironic beauty is populations below 40 years of the age elect their representatives who are above the age of 60. India would be the young democracy with the average age of 29 by 2020. In such a country the youth should realize it is a noble task to lead a country with vision, intelligence and knowledge of political process combined with a humane approach to the grass root problems of its citizens. The political strategies can be learnt from the seasoned politicians who are in their twilight years. Unfortunately the stigma on politics does not allow the majority of the youth to get into politics. We can have a look on the various factors of political picture, the role of education and the response of the youth towards their career.

5.1 THE PRESENT SCENARIO

The Indian youth is very much aware of the situation and problems of the country. In various instances we have seen the response of the youth towards the happenings in the country. For example the call against corruptions, scams, scandals, molestations, rapes or the regional issues on water or cultural and traditional practices. They do participate in demonstrations, dharanas, rallies, protests, street plays, candle-light marches, rail rokho and in many such similar awareness and protest activities. But after the event they go back to their own field and engage themselves in their private life until another call or situation arises. They do not show any interest to plunge into politics. What hinders the youth in doing so?

At the grass route level the youth has a question whether the field is suitable to them and will it make their career in politics is safe and successful. Middle class youth look forward for a safety corner. Government of India stated 22% of its population is below poverty line when the per capita income of 2013 was 58% higher than the median income of 2012. With this statement one could analyze that the youth is more concerned about the fiscal growth rather holding a public office. Average Indians have more pressing problems to deal with in their respective lives.

It is said that there are two types of youth in present politics. One of them is princely lineage and the other thug lineage. According to the ADR (Association for the Democratic Reforms) about 34% of M.P.s has criminal records. The middle class does not show any interest as they seem to be loyal and honest and would not like to dirty their hands.

While we see there is a large generation gap in the highest population and their leaders each of the generation has its own perspective being the politician. The older seasoned politicians are proud of their experience and expertise. They consider youth as inexperienced and would not understand the strategic moves in politics. Therefore the seasoned politicians should be

guiding the youth with their invaluable experience. But there is a good mix of energy and experience with those who are in their early 30s or early 40s. We need to understand that the genuine leaders of the country have travelled a long way with their hard work and service to the society.

Politics which has turned six decades of ruling has twisted and turned many a times even though the constitution of India is ultimate. The concept of Welfare State is one of the factors that speak of the success of a government and its governance. This factor is working in each every political party as the agenda of winning a election goes on this. But the Welfare State principles are inter- connected with caste, religion, society and politics. Money Muscle and Mafia goes hand in hand with politics. The political parties have youth associations as well some the associations of the students are patronized by the political parties. Youth are able to understand what is happening around the world. Those who participate in rallies, dharanas or protests for genuine cause are tried to pull in by the political parties. Catch them young and infuse the party agenda is the prime importance. A list of students unions and the parties which back them here below shows the inter relationship of the unions and the political parties.

All India Students Federation(AISF)	related to Communist Party of India
All Bodo Students Union (ABSU)	Revolutionary Socialist Unity
All Assam Students Union	Historically related to Asom Gana Parishad
All India Democratic Students Organisation	Socialist Unity Centre of India (Communist)

All India Progressive Students Union	Revolutionary Socialist Party
All India Progressive Students Union (Bolshevik)	Revolutionary Socialist Party (Bolshevik)
All India Revolutionary Students' Federation	Communist Party of India (Maoist)
Akhil Bharatiya Vidyarthi Parishad	Constitutionally Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh
All India Sikh Students Federation	Karnail Singh Peer Mohammad[1]

All India Students Association	Communist Party of India (Marxist–Leninist) Liberation
All India Students Bloc	All India Forward Bloc
All Kamtapuri Students Union	Kamtapur Peoples Party
Bahujan Samaj Student's Forum	Bahujan Samaj Party
Bharatiya Vidyarthi Sena	Shiv Sena
Biju Chhatra Janata Dal	Biju Janata Dal
Campus Front of India	Popular Front of India
Chhatra Bharati	Third Front and Anna Hazare
Chhatra Janata Dal (Secular)	Janata Dal (Secular)
Chhatra Lok Janshakti	Lok Janshakti Party
Chhatra Rashtriya Janata Dal	Rashtriya Janata Dal

Chhatra Yuva Sangharsh Samiti	Aam Aadmi Party
Concern	No affiliation
Gorkha Janmukti Vidhyarthi Morcha	Gorkha Janmukti Morcha
Hindu Vidyarthi Sabha Constitutionally independent but ideologically	close to Akhil Bharatiya Hindu Mahasabha
Indian National Student Organisation	Indian National Lok Dal
Muslim Students Federation	Independents' Consolidation[2]
Independent platform by the students of Presidency University, Kolkata	
Kerala state sunni Students Federation(SSF) students wing of samastha kerala jamiyyathul ulama	
Kerala Students Congress (Jacob)	Kerala Congress (Jacob)
Kerala Students Union	Indian National Congress
Maharashtra Navnirman Vidyarthi Sena	Maharashtra Navnirman Sena
MGJSM	Student wing of the Jacobite Syrian Christian Church
MGOCSM	Student wing of the Indian Orthodox Church
Mubarakpur Student Union	Mubarakpur
Muslim Students Organisation(MSO)	students wing of All India Sunni Jam-
Iyyathul Ulema	Indian Union Muslim League
Nationalist Students Congress	Nationalist Congress Party
National Students Union of India	Indian National Congress
Orissa Chhatra Parishad	Orissa Gana Parishad
Punjab University Students Union(PUSU)	Independent in Punjab
National Students League	Indian National League
Progressive Democratic Students Organisation	Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) in Andhra Pradesh
Progressive Democratic Students Union	Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) New Democracy in Andhra Pradesh & Punjab
Progressive Students' Federation of India	Revolutionary Communist Party of India
Radical Students Union	Communist Party of India (Maoist) in Andhra Pradesh
Rashtrawadi Vidyarthi Congress	Nationalist Congress Party
Republican Student Federation of India	Republican Party of India
Republican Students Union of India	Constitutionally Independent ideologically Socialist

Samyak Vidyarthi Andolan (SVA)	Bharip Bahujan Mahasangh (Adv.Prakash Ambedkar)
Samajwadi Chhatra Sabha	Samajwadi Party
Students Islamic Organisation of India	Jamaat-e-Islami Hind
Students' Federation of India	Communist Party of India (Marxist)
Student Union of India	Jai Jawan Jai Kisan Party
Student Organisation of India	Shiromani Akali Dal[3]
Student Organisation Of Panjab University (SOPU)	Independent in Punjab
Students Federation of India	related to Communist Party of India (Marxist)
Telugu Nadu Students Federation (TNSF)	Telugu Desam Party
Telangana Rashtra Vidyarthi Samithi	Telangana Rashtra Samithi
Trinamool Chhatra Parishad	Trinamool Congress
Twipra Students Federation	A Nationalist students organization of Tripura
National conference students union	Jammu & Kashmir National Conference
Technical students organization	Independent in Kerala
West Bengal State Chhatra Parishad	Indian National Congress
Gandhi Group Students Union	Independent Punjab University

Many a time the political party's blind fold these young energetic rash and dashing youth to fulfill their purpose rather than taking them to a proper track. In certain cases it could cause disruption to the system in the crucial time. At the same time the technically advanced students also play their role. For example when the demonetization took place the 'high tech' chip in two thousand rupee note became viral. It expressed the symptoms of dictatorship. As well it led for the hero worship. Finally RBI had to clarify that there is no such chip. In such cases either the students in their own interest to get popularity or they have been used to spread rumor. Sometimes it could be true but most of the time it is false. Young followers and the common man educated and uneducated are not able to analyze or find out the reality. The political parties have their own creative youth who make memes to tarnish the image of the opponents. The literature what they read is based on the principles what they believe or what they have been made to believe. By the time get vast knowledge and wide experience they would have worked for the same principles.

5.2 THE ROLE OF EDUCATION

India has produced good number of student leaders as politicians. Politics is considered as a skill and study how to govern and administrate a country as per the constitution. Education should help the youth to apply their own rationale. Of course Civics or political science is the curriculum of secondary and higher secondary level. At various levels the students learn about Legislature, Executive and Judiciary. At pre university level and there after political science becomes elective. There are different opinions regarding the introduction of civics and the suitable age of the student to understand the functioning of legislature, executive and judiciary. Some strongly oppose saying that at secondary level they are not able to understand. The others are of the opinion that they learn better when they are young and they could be motivated in a better manner to enter into politics and get experience of the service, sacrifice and leadership. As mentioned above at pre-university level and there after political science becomes elective the Supreme Court has made it mandatory to study Constitution of India and Human Rights at under graduate level. It gives the clear cut indication that everybody should know not only about the rights but duties as well the functioning of the governments according to the constitution.

The student councils should voice their problems and make use of the opportunities to express their leadership. Reduction of voting age has made the students as voters and the congregation as vote banks. Students who aspire for the entry into politics find that students union is the pathway for their endeavor. The awareness about the democratic process is good on the part of the students. The young minds will learn about the rights and duties, reservations and various articles stated in the constitution. Even though all of them do not enter into politics but take various professions will be an asset to the country so that whenever there is a need of them for the country they can get into politics. Universities shaping future politicians and guiding them to be the good leaders is a good move so that awareness about the politics and providing a forum for the future leaders. In every other field there is induction program, orientation, training and many other modes to make an aspirant suitable for his office. The sad state is of politics where any sort of preparatory programs are absent. Education aims to develop autonomous, critical thinking individuals and helps develop a just and democratic society is sharply political.

5.3 CHALLENGES AND FINDINGS

Youth entering into politics is matter of prominent decision. Generally there in no warm welcome to the youth in the world of politics for the right reasons. As there is a social stigma on politics the parents are not very keen to send their kin into the muck. In general present day youth is not finding any of the role models fitting to their ideology. At this stage no government or leader can take a u turn unwinding the religion, caste and society. Middle class youth have to achieve many things. They support their families to come up in life. They become heir not only to the ancestral property but to their debts too. The one who is pursuing higher education on loan hardly thinks of politics or its developments. His goal is to

get a good job and get rid of the debts. One of the studies on the Indian youth and politics that Indian Youth has no genuine interest to enter into politics. The older generations who are well versed in politics consider the youth as inexperienced and would not understand the strategic moves of politics. But those who are in their early thirties and late forties make a good blend of energy and experience. The seasoned politicians should guide the youth with their invaluable experience. But the absence of a role model to the youth is a real hiccup in the process of roping in the youth into politics. At grass root level the youth has a question whether the field of politics is suitable to them and will it make their career safe and successful. The skill of politics and its study in an organized movement can create a sound administration. The ignorance of politics among the citizens of a nation paves the way for the rise of tyranny and the fall of democracy.

Indian education system at the university level is highly politicized. Right from the appointment level, who should be at the helm of affairs to the point of allotment of hostel facility to the last student who had taken admission in that institution? Most of the departments are either the followers of some political parties or the political parties support the cause of the department. Political intrusion in universities gathered momentum in the past 25 years, and has now reached a stage that could be the edge of the precipice for public universities. The student leaders are roped in by the politicians. The student leader's words and thoughts are related and identified with the party agenda and the politician declares that the student leader would join the party and canvas for the party. Hardly the student leader has any time on hand to complete his study or accomplish his mission. In many universities election for the unions or councils is no less than any general election. Money, muscle and mafia works on the campus. The organizations that support the union leaders see that their party propaganda is taken care on the campus. There are instances where the politicians have laid their hands into the campus politics and the university authorities could not even raise their opinion. Unions of students, teachers and employees are instruments in political battles. Campuses were turned into spheres of influence for political parties. As the old public universities have declined without a pale shadow the existing universities are getting diluted in their standards.

6. SOLUTIONS

Universities are not mere classroom oriented. The students learn many more things other than their regular discipline. The exposure they get makes them the responsible citizens of the nation. For teachers again it is not limited to teaching and research but they create the torch bearers of the country. They being intellectuals bring in the qualities of independent thinking, bring forth credible voice in evaluating governments, parliament, legislature and the judiciary as the guardians of the society. The role of the university teachers is very important for a political democracy.

The experienced politicians should make way for the youngsters to get into politics. They should train them how manage a public office. Like a company or industry induction programs, coaching and training should be given to the spirants. Certain number of seats

right from the local self-government should be reserved for the youth. They should be assured of secure life and proper career. It is advisable that a constitutional amendment can be made to have minimum education for the politicians and a age limit to retire from the office. Forums and stages to be given in the higher educational institutions to churn the ideas of youth their by to quench their thirst for knowledge and bring out excellence in them. Exchange programs with other countries on political science to be organized. There by youth should find it a field to serve the nation and not the other way round.

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